

COVERAGE OF LIVESTOCK ISSUES IN “AVESTO”

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Annotation: In this article, the sacred book of Zoroastrianism “Avesta” deals with customs, ceremonies related to livestock, the main livestock of Khorezm oasis residents, and issues related to the importance of cattle breeding in society.

Keywords: livestock, religion, agriculture, inhabitants, herdsman, ceremonies, customs, religious beliefs, pasture

Among scientists, there is an opinion that the religion of Zoroastrianism first appeared in the environment of herding communities. Also, since the oldest archaeological complexes in Central Asia were found in Ancient Khorezm, S.P. Tolstov put forward the idea that the first homeland of Zoroastrianism was the land of Khorezm in the 40s of the 20th century. This idea has its place in science even now.

According to “Avesta”, the Aryans were the free, warrior class of the community in social life, they were the rulers, guardians and masters of the country. This class and its members, in contrast to their clans and other tribesmen, are referred to in “Avesta” as free, that is, Aryans. The land where they lived was called Aryanam Vaychah, the homeland of the Aryans, the Aryan expanse. The main wealth of the people of this country is livestock, that is, cattle, horses, camels, sheep, goats and donkeys. The daily lifestyle of the Arys is built on the basis of nomadic pastoralism typical of steppe people [1].

Humans tamed and domesticated animals, and over time began to use them to plow the land. With the development of agriculture using the plow, breeding of domestic animals also began to develop. Cattle farming appeared. In the past, cattle breeding served to meet the needs of man for meat. And the consumption of milk is started much later. “In Zoroastrianism, cow's milk is considered divine. Zoroastrian's mother started drinking cow's milk and khaoma drink,” writes S.P. Tolstov. In the

“Videvdat” part of “Avesta” there are such words: “Happy is the husband who builds a house, such a husband is the richest husband” [2].

A new social stratum related to land ownership began to appear within the society. During this period, a great phenomenon of migration occurred on a global scale. Attacks of nomadic and semi-sedentary tribes on the ocre, agricultural regions increased. Gross invasions had a negative impact on the economy in general, and livestock in particular. Despite this, Khorezm people continued trade relations with their neighbors.

The expression “urkach” in “Avesta” is related to camel breeding, which is believed to have originated at the border of the Eneolithic and Bronze Ages. The likeness of the waves of the water to the scythe seems to repeat the image taken from the camel's appearance. So, the history of the formation of this "Yasht" is also very ancient. Judging from the point of view that the “Yashts” are chronologically older than the “Gots” in the “Avesta”, the period of training the horse is correspondingly ancient.

In “Avesta” the ancient inhabitants of Central Asia are mentioned as Turs (Turonians). In “Avesta” it is given as “Thura”. The ethnonym “Tur”, first mentioned in “Avesta”, was later associated with cattle-breeding population living in steppes and mountains of Central Asia. According to scientists, the concept of species may be the original name of the Sak-massagets [1].

The society in which “Avesta” was created coincided with the period when patriarchal relations developed in ancient Khorezm and the first buds of statehood appeared. According to “Avesto” information, this society is a herdsman and a semi-sedentary and semi-sedentary peasant society, whose main property - wealth was livestock, arable land and pastures. The peoples living here raised a large number of camels, bighorn cattle, sheep and goats, and all property relations were built on the ownership of livestock, pastures, and arable land. The members of the community were gradually divided into rich herdsmen and those with little or no livestock. The class of rich herders formed a kind of herder military aristocracy. As a result of

internecine wars, those who were captured were turned into slaves. In this regard, stratification took place, and the society was divided into priests, soldiers, members of the common community, livestock owners, landowners and slaves.

The administration of the country was carried out on the basis of bottom-up subordination through a hierarchical system. In this, the patriarchal big family headed by the father was called “dmanu”. That is, the father, the guardian of the house, becomes a village community on the basis of kinship, and this is called “vis”. “Vis” were managed by the village elder vispati. Several vis united into a tribal association. This was called zantu and was ruled by zantupati. Finally, the union of the Zantus was called a dayu and was ruled by a dahyupati. Socio-political union of Dayu type was the first stage of our territorial statehood in our country.

Cattle-raising tribes settled near water sources and began to engage in agriculture. In agriculture, a lot of attention is paid to the cultivation of cereals, which are an important source of food for people and livestock. In order to create artificial pastures and meadows in Khorezm, the area of alfalfa and other nutritious crops has been regularly expanded. In exchange for this, livestock farming has been developing as a sector. Of course, we believe that it would be an honor to study such an ancient and extremely interesting history and apply useful instructions to the present and future life.

In the lower Zarafshan and Amudarya oasis steppes, where livestock has developed, it is observed that traditional livestock has been preserved in the character of high productivity. First of all, in these regions, livestock and farming oases did not have fixed boundaries. As a result of complementing each other of the two types of farms, the development of livestock farming is observed in one way or another. Secondly, the mutual complementation of the two farm types stimulated the processes of double assimilation and activated the economy of the settled and semi-settled population.

Since ancient times, since the beginning of the process of taming and domesticating animals, shepherds have also widely celebrated rituals and customs

related to livestock. At the same time, the relationship between man and nature, between people and the animal world, has been reflected in the life experiences and spiritual views of the human society, which have been related to the cocktail activity for thousands of years. As we mentioned above, animal husbandry is an ancient type of occupation, and since the early times of human history, beliefs related to animals have become important in the way of life of the population. “Avesta”, the holy book of Zoroastrian religion, emphasizes the special attention and care of livestock, especially horses, cattle and small ungulates.

The essence of rituals and traditions related to cattle breeding and their main goals, that is, the rituals and traditions include raising livestock, protecting it from various diseases, pestilence, wild beasts and thieves. Livestock health has always been of great importance to cattle breeders. Shepherds used to perform various rituals and customs at a certain time of the year in order to protect the cattle from all kinds of calamities, evil forces, evil eyes, damage and attacks of wild animals. It is necessary to classify each category of ceremonies and traditions into several groups. We also preferred a simple division based on the calendrical norm in the classification of rituals related to cattle breeding, and divided them into two groups. The first group includes rituals and customs that are performed from the time of driving the cattle to the summer pasture in the spring and returning from the summer pasture to the village in the fall; and the second group includes various ceremonies, customs and rituals, from the process of returning the sheep from the village to the time of going to the summer pasture in the spring. Information about this can be found in Eastern and Western, that is, Chinese, Indian, Persian-Iranian literature.

Thus, the ancient Khorezm people achieved great success in livestock as well as achieving high culture in agriculture. There is no doubt that agriculture played an important economic role in the farms of settled Khorezm people. Because well-developed livestock was an important source of food for the peasant. Therefore, the agriculture and livestock of this region were a complementary and mutually reinforcing system. In the lower part of Amudarya, we can consider that fishing was

also a complex economy. The inhabitants of this part of the Khorezm oasis, who were in constant contact with the tribes and peoples of the desert, adapted to the natural conditions in a semi-sedentary state, combined farming with animal husbandry and fishing crafts.

Livestock issues of the people who lived in our country in ancient times were expressed in the famous book “Avesta”. It is known that this holy book is the first unique source about the peoples of Central Asia. The oldest tribes of “Avesta” lived by livestock. The book contains a lot of information about the life of a cattle rancher: “Turning to Ahuramazda, the prophet said: “You are the one who gave birth and created the cattle that are the source of our life.”

“In all the creations of Akhuramaza, livestock is in the first place. We call for “peaceful grazing and feeding” for the livestock” . Livestock needs a good owner. I will provide free movement and free life to the livestock owners of this land.

Livestock was one of the oldest forms of traditional economic activities and one of the main types of work that determined the source of livelihood. The way of life of cattle breeders and the views and customs related to this occupation have been studied to a certain extent based on ethnographic materials. However, the ancient religious ideas and beliefs related to livestock have not been specially researched so far as a separate research object. After all, from ancient times, that is, from the beginning of the process of training and domestication of animals, the attitude of the people to the animal world was reflected in the rituals and traditions related to livestock. At the same time, the relationship between man and nature, between people and the animal world, the life experiences of the human society related to several thousand years of work, the relationship to space and time, spiritual views and, of course, the religious beliefs of that time are reflected. What is important for

us at this point are the religious views in the animal husbandry rituals, more precisely, the traditions and rituals related to pre-Islamic religious beliefs and views.

As mentioned above, livestock is a very ancient type of occupation, and cults and beliefs related to animals have been important in people's lifestyle since the beginning of human history. In the sacred book of Zoroastrianism, "Avesta", the religious attitude towards livestock, especially horses, cattle and domestic animals with small hooves is explained. Cattle breeders were considered believers. In particular, in the texts of "Avesta" the patron saint of small animals is mentioned under the name Frodat-Fshova. Zoroastrian asked Ahuramazda, "Where is the fourth place in the world that is happier than all?" - when asked, Ahuramazda answered: "Such a place is the land where the herd of yaks and herds of tevayaar are cared for the most".

We will try to analyze in more detail the ancient religious beliefs related to animal husbandry and the customs and ceremonies related to them, which are found in the lifestyle of the Uzbeks of the Fergana Valley. Ferghana Valley residents have been engaged in farming along with animal husbandry since ancient times. Cattle breeding was one of the main and leading economic sectors in the mountainous, sub-mountainous and steppe areas of the valley. Livestock animals together with herdsmen have an important role in the life of the agricultural population. Farmers used them mainly as labor force, catch, auxiliary force and additional source of income. There was a main purpose and the essence of rituals and customs related to livestock. That is, the rituals are aimed at breeding livestock, protecting it from various diseases, pestilence, wild beasts and thieves. Therefore, the health of livestock has always been important for breeders. They performed various ceremonies at a certain time of the year in order to protect the cattle from all kinds of calamities, evil forces, evil eyes and attacks of wild animals.

We also considered a simple division based on the calendrical norm in the classification of animal husbandry rituals and studied this series of rituals in two groups. The first group includes rituals and customs performed during the period

from driving the cattle to the summer pasture in the spring and returning from the summer pasture to the village in the fall, while the second group includes various ceremonies and customs from the process of returning the cattle from the winter pasture to the time of the departure to the summer pasture in the spring [3].

Folklorist scientist B. Sarimsokov writes that Uzbeks used two different year calendars in their work. These calendars were governed by the beginning and end of people's livestock and farming activities. So, Uzbeks have two different year calculations, which are defined as follows: the farmer's year starts on March 22, and the shepherd's year starts on March 16. In fact, after March 22, in the conditions of Central Asia, the soil will dry up and the plants will be affected. The beginning of the Shepherd's year on March 16 is also associated with the beginning of the earth and the beginning of grass growth. From this day, the herdsmen start the work of clearing the summer pasture". Among the herdsmen of the Fergana Valley, with the arrival of the shepherd year, the cattle were taken out of the countryside to summer pastures.

In conclusion, animal husbandry is one of the most ancient forms of Uzbek economic activities, and the sacred book of Zoroastrian religion "Avesta" explains the religious attitude towards livestock, especially horses, cattle and small hooved domestic animals. According to "Avesta" information, this society is a herdsman and a semi-sedentary and semi-sedentary peasant society, whose main property - wealth was livestock, plowed lands and pastures.

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